

Evaluating the Logistic Performance Capability of Regeneration Processes

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Abstract : For years now, it has been recognized that logistic performance capability contributes enormously to a production enterprise's competitiveness and as such is a critical control lever. In doing so, the orientation on customer wishes (e.g. delivery dates) represents a key parameter not only in the value-adding production but also in product regeneration. Since production and regeneration processes have different characteristics, production planning and control measures cannot be directly transferred to regeneration processes. As part of a special research project, the Institute of Production Systems and Logistics Hannover is focused on increasing the logistic performance capability of regeneration processes for complex capital goods. The aim is to ensure logistic targets are met by implementing a model specifically designed to align the capacities and load in regeneration processes.

Keywords : capacity planning, complex capital goods, logistic performance, regeneration process

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